

Customer Perception and Expectation Regarding Transformation through E-Delivery Channels of Bank

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Abstract: The aim of this quantitative study to analyse the perception and expectations of customers regarding e- delivery channels of bank. Structured questions were asked through questionnaire from total 600 customers of public as well as private sector banks of Punjab state. Quantitative content analysis was used to analyse the data. The paper investigates the perceptions of customers regarding quality of e-services, frequency of usage and adoption of modern technology based e-channels, frauds, problems faced, preferences and future of e-delivery channels. The corona virus pandemic has triggered the hike in the use of e-delivery channels even after the crisis. The results of χ^2 test were found partially significant regarding customer perception and expectation regarding e-channels. The study suggests financial literacy, more transparency, innovative banking solutions, mitigating the risk of frauds to enhance customer experience.

Keywords: Customers, E-delivery channels, Technology

1. Introduction

Banking sector is passing through crucial stage of transformation where all the vision of working are changing speedily and technology is the dominant factor which helped the bank to have blend of knowledge and innovative products and services to win the competitive market. Customer preferences change with change in policies and regulations of the ruling elite as evidenced during demonetisation regime. Customers today have variety of offers, options and opportunities while choosing banking services (Sunith, 2019). The major transformation in banks during pandemic period is drastic increase in usage and awareness level regarding e-delivery channels of bank. People who were reluctant to move to electronic banking application are now considering the shift on easy mode. Technology trust has been proven to be critical for Customer Relation Management (CRM) performance (Mansour et. al., 2022). More the economy is prone towards cashless payments, more they are contributing towards paying taxes in advance. Shopping through debit cards is highly dependent on demographic factors (Chandravati, 2017). Age is the major variable that influence the use of internet banking services especially the age group between 25 years to 40 years plays an important role in their day to day activity. Male users of internet services are more than female (Melvin, 2018). Demographic factor like

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education had laid great significance on the adoption of digital payment system (Shamsher and Ravish, 2017). Other elements such as customer's demographic background such as age, monthly income also influence the adoption of debit card by consumers (Norhayati et al. 2017).

The study identified key challenges like increasing competition, customer retention, system and security, rising expectation (Mansour et. al., 2022). Problems like inaccessibility/failure to avail e-banking services due to lack of proper knowledge, misuse of ATM cards and various other types of thefts and cybercrimes involved. However, some strategies were also suggested to overcome the problems faced like customer education, seminars/ meetings, proper network, and infrastructural facilities, ensure proper working of ATM machines to widen the scope of e-banking services (Uppal, 2019).

The study is designed to analyse the perception of customers towards e-delivery channels of bank, to examine the adoption level and preferred e-delivery channels by customers and to identify the frequency of complaints of customer regarding e-delivery.

3. Methodology

To measure the objectives, exploratory research sampling technique is used to analyse the finding of the empirical data. In this study, the researcher tried to analyse the perceptions and expectations of customer of Punjab region towards e-delivery channels on three selected locations of Punjab namely Ludhiana, Jalandhar and Bathinda.

Top two banks from public sector and top two banks from private sector was taken for the study based on maximum number of bank branches in the Punjab state. The study was based on primary as well as secondary data. The researcher studied a reasonable sample of 600 bank customers (300 from each group). The study have taken into account the responses of both male and female as the study is not gender specific

The study included only major categories of e-services like ATM, Credit card, Internet Banking, Mobile Banking, Tele banking, UPI/BHIM, E-wallets like Paytm, Mobikwik etc., Voice technology, SMS banking, Online portal services like opening of account/disbursement of loan etc. , Missed call banking on the basis of their penetration. The study was based upon perception and expectations of consumers towards banks (public and private each).

4. Data Analysis

The data collected regarding various e-delivery channels are analysed as follows

Table 1: Preference of using various e-delivery channels

Type of e-service	Type of Bank	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Very Often	Total	Weight Mean	χ^2	p-value
ATM	Public bank	1	14	36	101	148	300	4.40	18.687	.001**
	Private bank	1	8	24	67	200	300			
Credit Card	Public bank	13	30	84	89	84	300	3.95	43.504	.0001**
	Private bank	3	14	45	86	152	300			
Internet Banking	Public bank	7	24	72	109	88	300	3.89	5.595	.231
	Private bank	7	16	71	94	112	300			
Mobile Banking	Public bank	13	21	56	90	120	300	3.88	10.794	.029*
	Private bank	6	33	61	108	92	300			
Tele Banking	Public bank	69	72	102	41	16	300	2.77	27.976	.0001**
	Private bank	35	69	88	78	30	300			
UPI/BHIM	Public bank	53	58	82	64	43	300	3.40	70.924	.0001**
	Private bank	23	26	54	71	126	300			
E-Wallet	Public bank	20	34	58	100	88	300	3.88	27.799	.0001**
	Private bank	12	18	52	70	148	300			
Voice technology	Public bank	107	83	70	24	16	300	2.37	20.391	.0001**
	Private bank	88	54	86	52	20	300			
SMS Banking	Public bank	69	100	66	36	29	300	2.69	23.965	.0001**
	Private bank	44	75	85	72	24	300			
Online Opening of account	Public bank	48	83	105	43	21	300	2.90	24.735	.0001**
	Private bank	36	64	82	67	51	300			
Online disbursement of loan	Public bank	69	84	65	46	36	300	2.70	11.219	.024*
	Private bank	62	62	98	49	29	300			
Missed call banking	Public bank	106	95	61	19	19	300	2.50	49.897	.0001**
	Private bank	60	59	89	56	36	300			

Source: developed on the basis of primary data

- It is concluded that consumers of both public as well as private sector banks prefer to use ATM more often which means there is a significant association between frequency of use of ATM services in Public and Private sector banks.
- It is concluded that consumers of private sector banks use credit cards more frequently than that of public sector banks due to numerous offers like exciting discounts, rewards, accidental death cover, fire and burglary protection on items that you have purchased and other facilities provided by private banks.
- It is concluded that internet banking of both public sector as well as private sector banks is popular mainly among customers of business class only. Also internet banking provides limited number of facilities. That's why only few number of customers use it on frequent basis which means there is no significant association between frequency of use of Internet banking services in Public and Private sector banks.
- The survey reveals that performance of mobile banking is satisfactory and customers of both public as well as private sector banks prefer it highly.
- It is concluded that UPI/BHIM mode of payment is preferred by only a few customers.
- The survey examines that e-wallets like Paytm, Phone Pay, google pay are preferred and used by majority of customers because they are time saving and apart from sending and receiving money these apps have various other features like recharge of mobile, to pay electricity bill, to book gas cylinder, to book flight tickets and many more. But still some customers lack adequate knowledge and they refrain to use it due to illiteracy.
- The study reveals that voice technology of banking is still not popular among customers of banks. Majorly respondents were not aware of it.
- It is concluded that performance of SMS banking is satisfactory among customers of bank. The push messages provide them notifications/ informational messages which includes alerts such as amount credited/debited in account, cash withdrawals etc. The pull messages of bank provide OTPs for processing payments with security. However some consumers don't use it because of lack of proper knowledge.
- The study reveals that those customers who want to avail loan facility always prefer to visit bank branch physically to understand all the terms and conditions of loan disbursement rather than taking it online.
- Through the above given discussion Objective-1 has been justified that Hypothesis i.e. **“There is no significant difference in customers' preference towards various e-services”** is partially accepted.

Table 2: Frequency of complaints faced by customers using various e-delivery channels

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Very Often	Total	Weight Mean	χ^2	p-value
ATM	26	101	153	150	170	600	3.56	31.141	.0001
	4.3%	16.8%	25.5%	25.0%	28.3%	100.0%			
Credit card	23	135	180	129	133	600	3.36	4.902	.297
	3.8%	22.5%	30.0%	21.5%	22.2%	100.0%			
Internet banking	18	116	216	143	107	600	3.34	14.267	.006
	3.0%	19.3%	36.0%	23.8%	17.8%	100.0%			
Mobile Banking	18	134	215	144	89	600	3.25	23.363	.0001
	3.0%	22.3%	35.8%	24.0%	14.8%	100.0%			
Tele-banking	101	160	223	75	41	600	2.66	79.187	.0001
	16.8%	26.7%	37.2%	12.5%	6.8%	100.0%			
UPI/BHIM	98	153	188	87	74	600	2.81	46.975	.0001
	16.3%	25.5%	31.3%	14.5%	12.3%	100.0%			
E-Wallet	56	102	203	102	137	600	3.27	11.297	.023
	9.3%	17.0%	33.8%	17.0%	22.8%	100.0%			
Voice technology	141	138	242	49	30	600	2.48	40.077	.0001
	23.5%	23.0%	40.3%	8.2%	5.0%	100.0%			
SMS Banking	92	133	202	89	84	600	2.90	69.814	.0001
	15.3%	22.2%	33.7%	14.8%	14.0%	100.0%			
Online Opening of account/loan	76	139	245	99	41	600	2.82	29.218	.0001
	12.7%	23.2%	40.8%	16.5%	6.8%	100.0%			
Missed call banking	112	127	233	79	49	600	2.71	51.589	.0001
	18.7%	21.2%	38.8%	13.2%	8.2%	100.0%			

Source: Developed on the basis of primary data.

- The result drawn from survey is that customer faces many problems of ATM machines that do not provide convenient knowledge to every customer who are using ATM machine. ATM is most popularly used but have various problems like machine is out of order, machine is out of cash , problem while cash deposit , faulty dispenser like cash gets stuck inside cash box and transaction stand unsuccessful due to some technical glitch and the issue is resolved by branch in 2-3 days.
- It is concluded that number of cash deposit machines are very limited in number as per requirement.
- The study reveals that performance of credit card is found satisfactory sometimes repayments may be late but overall the quality of service provided by credit card is considered good by customers.
- The study shows that internet banking and mobile banking often causes trouble to consumers. The reason is mainly due to server down of bank, technical errors, software glitch, weak internet connectivity and online frauds.
- The conclusion is drawn from the survey although e wallets like paytm, google pay, phone pay, and UPI transactions are cost and time saving for customers but yet there are several security and safety issues faced by customers. E wallets can lead to credit and debit card fraud, missing transactions, fake websites are masquerading as being from mobile wallets and the leaking of banking details. Customer mind set, lack of trust, lack of awareness, technological issues are the other issues faced by customers.
- Through the above given discussion Objective-2 has been justified that Hypothesis i.e. **“There is no significant difference in frequency of complaints towards e-services”** is partially accepted.

5. Customer Expectations: Customer Findings

- The result depicts that ATM kiosk and cash deposit machines should be installed at more frequent locations so that customers can access anytime and everywhere. Also, machines should ensure security and privacy. There must not be overcrowding in ATM machines.
- It is expected by customers that banks should invest in marketing efforts to build awareness for online options. This should include clear communication, targeted campaigns, financial advice and tutorials. Banks should take adequate steps and programmes to strengthen financial literacy especially in the rural areas. Banks should provide innovative banking solutions to improve customer experience.

- It is highly expected by customers that banks should take necessary covid precautions and follow safety and security procedure in the bank.
- The customer expects that banking apps should be notifications based like other mobile applications which send a pop-up notification on customer's mobile whenever there is something new added.
- The customer expects that banks should take adequate steps to mitigate the chances of fraud, and strengthen their security base to ensure safe banking for customers.
- It is expected that banks should take adequate steps to reduce financial stress of customers whenever needed. They may consider waiving interest charges and suspending late-account fees for customers who request changes in case of emergency like covid-19 or etc.
- The study shows that banks should focus on building customer trust and brand loyalty by delivering them good customer experiences, receiving and responding to their feedback.

6. Conclusion

Customers of financial services are changing in terms of their wants, need, desires and expectations. Customers have more choices and are rightfully more demanding. They have lots of choices when selecting financial products. In conformity with these changes, there would be changes in bank's services, training, attitude, marketing strategies and terms of organisation and control therefore, financial solutions need to be built around the customer. Pandemic has undoubtedly acted as a catalyst for digitizing financial practices.

In the above study it is found that how technology has led the transformation in Indian banking sector. Technology has proved to be a wake-up call for banks and those that heed will be able to leverage customer experience as a strategic differentiator. The study concludes that technology had made customers more tech savvy and their reference benchmarks are evolving. So their needs require the speed of innovation. Besides using ATM, debit cards and credit cards customers have also preferred to use e channels, e-wallets, online KYC and many other services. The options of other e-channels like voice technology is still to pick up in a big way. Thus the study concludes that customers are partially satisfied with the efficient services provided by e-delivery channels of banks. So, we can say that future of e-delivery channels of bank have wide scope.

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